

**THE ROLE OF SCHOOLS in ENHANCING the WELL-BEING of STUDENTS
AFFECTED BY WAR**

Savaşta Etkilenen Öğrencilerin Refahını Artırmada Okulların Rolü

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Abstract

This comprehensive study analyzes the importance and role of schools in improving the well-being of students in grades IX, X and XI who have experienced trauma and distress due to war in schools located on the former front line in the Agdam region. In light of the results of the survey conducted with the students, their social, emotional and psychological conditions are investigated under the headings of "student emotions" and "school environment". The research findings emphasize that the courses and extracurricular activities offered by schools can increase the spiritual and intellectual well-being of students. These courses and activities will positively affect the emotional and social development of students and help them overcome the stress, fear and trauma they experienced during the war. The results suggest that, based on international experience, various improvements can be made in different directions to improve the well-being of students in these former front line schools and to transform them into productive environments for students.

Key Words: armed conflict, war trauma, student well-being, role of school, Agdam region

Öz

Bu kapsamlı çalışma, Ağdam bölgesindeki eski cephe hattında yer alan okullarda savaş nedeniyle travma ve sıkıntı yaşayan IX, X ve XI. sınıflardaki öğrencilerin refahını iyileştirmede okulların önemini ve rolünü analiz etmektedir. Öğrencilerle yapılan anket sonuçları ışığında onların sosyal, duygusal ve psikolojik durumları "öğrenci duyguları" ve "okul ortamı" başlıkları altında araştırılıyor. Araştırma bulguları, okulların sunduğu derslerin ve ders dışı etkinliklerin öğrencilerin ruhsal ve entelektüel refahını artırabileceğini vurgulamaktadır. Bu ders ve aktiviteler öğrencilerin duygusal ve sosyal gelişimlerini olumlu yönde etkileyerek savaş sırasında yaşadıkları stres, korku ve travmayı aşmalarına yardımcı olacaktır. Sonuçlar, uluslararası deneyimlere dayanarak eskiden ön cephede yer alan bu okullardaki öğrencilerin refahını artırmak ve onları öğrenciler için verimli bir ortama dönüştürmek amacıyla farklı yönlerde çeşitli iyileştirmeler yapılabileceğini önermektedir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Silahlı çatışma, savaş travması, öğrenci refahı, okulun rolü, Ağdam bölgesi.

INTRODUCTION

According to the relevant provisions of the United Nations (UN) Convention on the Rights of the Child (1990), every child has the right to grow up healthily, survive, and receive an education, which is a primary obligation of the state they live in. However, armed conflicts affecting education occur in many parts of the world. Although education continues in conflict zones, this directly negatively impacts the quality of education. During wars, either schools are destroyed, students are killed, or students are forced to leave their homes due to the conflict, thus being deprived of their right to education (Gencer, 2017).

For 30 years, during the armed conflict between Azerbaijan and Armenia, thousands of students attended hundreds of schools in the border and frontline areas. Looking at this issue from the perspective of the Aghdam region alone, it can be seen that before the occupation (until 1993), there were 99 schools, 2,966 teachers, and 29,478 students operating in the Aghdam district (Ibrahimova, 2022). However, after 70% of the district's territory was occupied, 20 villages of the Aghdam district turned into frontline areas from 1993, and the schools in these villages became frontline educational institutions. During the war, schools were used as military bases. During the ceasefire, institutions were repeatedly damaged due to ceasefire violations. In the "April Battles" of 2016 and the "Patriotic War" of 2020, schools in the villages of Sarijali, Garadaghli, Mahrizli, Gul Baharli, and the settlement of Baharli in the frontline areas of the Aghdam district were destroyed by artillery strikes. During the ceasefire violations, 34 students fell victim to Armenian terror and mines, of which 14 died and 20 were injured (Ibrahimova, 2022).

Problem

During the Karabakh conflict, students were kept away from education, and their schools were subjected to armed attacks, negatively affecting their emotional and psychological well-being. As a result of these impacts, students' academic performance declined, and the number of students exhibiting negative behaviors in schools increased. Schools find it challenging to address these problems (Karakoç, 2022). Generally, the effects of war on children can be listed as follows: 1. Death, 2. Injury, 3. Disability, 4. Diseases and Psychological Trauma, 5. School Dropout.

Due to war and ceasefire violations, schools can sometimes be closed, resulting in students dropping out of education. The Patriotic War in Azerbaijan from September 27 to November 10, 2020, affected 594,700 students living in those regions. Additionally, observations by the International Committee of the Red Cross (ICRC, 2021) showed that children's love for life and their belief that the world is safe and just have been lost.

Research Questions

- 1 What is the well-being level of students affected by war?
- 2 What factors in the school affect student well-being?

1. Armed Conflict and Education

Armed conflicts and wars continue to occur in various regions of the world, impacting people not only socially and economically but also by depriving them of their

fundamental right to live, thrive, and most importantly, receive education (Baran, 2021). As conflicts affect every aspect of life, they also have numerous negative impacts on education. The initial effects include the deaths and injuries of students and teachers, the destruction of schools, and children receiving education in hazardous environments. According to a report by UNICEF (2017), armed conflicts have had a more significant impact on children in South Sudan. Many people have been forced to leave their homes and fight against hunger. Schools in the country have been looted, destroyed, or used for military purposes. Many teachers and students have been subjected to violence by militants, killed, or forcibly recruited into armed groups. These data suggest that education workers and learners are among the most affected by armed conflict. Thousands of students have been killed, over 2 million have been displaced from their homes, more than 2,300 have been injured, and approximately 19,000 have been forcibly recruited into armed groups. Additionally, gender-based violence and social problems have been observed due to armed conflict (Muthanna et al., 2022). Despite Turkey's efforts to enroll Syrian children in schools, there are still children who are out of school. About 41% of school-age Syrian refugee children have not been enrolled in the education process, indicating that approximately 450,000 school-age children are out of school. This also means that these children are at risk. Therefore, it is crucial to identify and enroll these children in the education process (Gencer, 2017).

During the six-week conflict in 2020 between Armenian and Azerbaijani forces and the de facto "Nagorno-Karabakh security forces," more than 130 schools and kindergartens were hit or disbanded. Both sides reportedly used armed forces and the factually "Nagorno-Karabakh security forces" in schools. Additionally, during the conflict, 54 Azerbaijani schools were damaged or destroyed. According to the Azerbaijani government, several children's gardens, vocational schools, and art schools were hit. All of these attacks occurred within the internationally recognized borders of Azerbaijan. In Armenia, two schools were damaged by explosive weapons during the fighting (GCPEA, 2022).

2. War Traumas

War has been a pervasive trauma observed for many years, with internal and external conflicts still ongoing in many countries. Wars impact the country where they occur primarily, but they can also negatively affect many countries without geographical or cultural connections (Karakoç, 2022). The most sensitive group affected by the long-term negative effects of war are children and adolescents. They are subjected to violence during wars and become dependent on others. Children left orphaned are placed in orphanages and shelters. While 92% of children worldwide attend primary school, only 61% of refugee children are able to attend primary school, and while 84% of children globally attend secondary school, only 23% of refugee children attend secondary school (Kılıç & Özkor, 2019). In South Sudan, the civil war not only caused damage to schools but also directly targeted students and teachers from 2013 to 2017. Attacks occurred in schools, and students, teachers, and school administrators were killed. More than 300 students were abducted from schools. Over thirty teachers were imprisoned for protesting the lack of salary during the civil war. Non-state armed groups in the Juba region forcibly recruited students from schools, resulting in their use in warfare. This

resulted in children being used in warfare. The majority of students recruited for combat were under 18 years old. It was noted in a United Nations report that girls cooking in abandoned homes and engaged in cleaning in refugee camps were subjected to sexual violence (Baran, 2020).

Continued conflicts can lead families and communities to take harmful steps such as early marriages. This is considered sexual violence against adolescents. Furthermore, the creation of distrust among different religious or ethnic groups due to conflicts also results in the disruption of societal structures and the breakdown of structures (Jordans et al., 2018).

In general, children face depression, anxiety, distress, post-traumatic stress disorder, and other psychological problems in the context of war. When children's health is exposed to such complex effects, the absence of access to formal or non-formal education further increases risks to their protection and well-being. School attendance helps restore psychological and social normality, provides social support and care through positive interactions with peers and educators, and creates opportunities for the formation of important life skills. Therefore, war and conflict exacerbate the negative impact on the lives of children living in former conflict zones, deepening their psychological traumas (Babayeva & Öməröva, 2022).

3. The Role of School in Student Well-being

Forming a strong character is considered one of the main objectives of families, schools, and society. The role of schools, in particular, is crucial in achieving this (Bayramlı, 2023). The development of education in societies depends on the solid foundation of education, and this development is based on the education provided. School is not only the basis for the formation of fundamental education but also a socialization space (Bayramlı, 2023).

Student well-being conceptually considers the necessity of teaching and training processes based on the principles of love, compassion, and social responsibility (Seden et al., 2020). A good school is one that fosters student well-being. The main task of modern schools is to increase student well-being through teacher and parent collaboration, creating conditions for their happiness and establishing a supportive environment (Aulia, 2018).

Research shows that the love, care, and support shown by teachers contribute to the elevation of classroom well-being (Seden et al., 2020). According to students, an environment conducive to effective learning should be provided in the classroom, their physical, psychological, emotional, and academic needs should be met, and equal opportunities should be created. Class environments based on positive student-teacher relationships improve outcomes. Factors that strengthen student-teacher and student-student relationships are mutual understanding, mutual trust, and care (Seden et al., 2020). It is necessary to know the importance of the classroom environment and the environment in which the student lives for student well-being. In this context, continuous work among children and adolescents, who are the most sensitive group among the population affected by conflicts and extraordinary situations, is essential (Baker et al., 2016). Also, it is considered necessary to take adequate steps to protect their mental health and psychosocial well-being. According to international education reports, school-

based support programs can help restore the majority of children and adolescents affected by conflict or disaster (Baker et al., 2016). Educational institutions are not only places of learning but also institutions that guarantee the social and emotional well-being of adolescents. Particularly, removing psychological traumas caused by stressful events in conflict areas falls on the school. For this purpose, schools conduct certain monitoring, diagnose students, and organize appropriate support programs (Baker et al., 2016). These programs help children and adolescents reduce traumatic symptoms and support them in overcoming loss, fear, and stress (UNICEF, 2016). Research conducted in many countries shows that the social and emotional knowledge and skills of teachers affect the psychosocial condition of children and help address their psychological health problems positively (UNICEF, 2016).

In 2021, in Azerbaijan, webinars of 4 academic hours each were organized for 1025 parents (40 groups) from conflict-affected areas on mental health and psychosocial well-being, enhancing children's psychosocial well-being, supportive communication methods, and other topics (ARTİ, 2021). During the webinars organized to help parents support the mental health and psychological well-being of children affected by conflict and to provide positive parenting, information was provided to parents about mental health and psychosocial well-being, stress responses of children of various ages during crises, and indicators of stress. Recommendations were also given to parents to develop supportive communication to enhance children's emotional intelligence and provide psychosocial support to children facing crises. Additionally, video clips prepared for parents within the framework of the project were showcased during the webinars (ARTİ, 2021). It is evident that, on a national scale, and especially for students who have suffered from war, enhancing their well-being is one of the current issues in education. For this purpose, special efforts are made with students in former conflict zones, programs are developed and implemented for the development of their psychological and emotional well-being (ARTİ, 2021).

METHODOLOGY

This research investigates the well-being of students affected by war in schools located along the former front line in the Aghdam district. During the research, a community approach was used to determine the well-being level of students in schools located in the war zone. The description of the community approach belongs to the qualitative research method. This method provides insights into the phenomenon and describes the situation (Shahbazov, 2019). In the community approach, the researcher works with numbers and figures (Shahbazov, 2019). When implementing the community approach, a survey was conducted among students to assess their well-being levels.

FINDINGS

The purpose of this research was to study the well-being of students affected by war. For this purpose, a target group of 782 students enrolled in grades IX, X, and XI of 10 rural schools located in the former frontline area of Aghdam, which were exposed to attacks during both ceasefire and wartime, was selected. Due to the utilization of the convenience sampling method in this research project, the students answered a questionnaire consisting of 34 questions. A total of 716 students participated in the

survey. The questions were presented to the target group under two main headings: "Student Emotions" and "School Environment."

1. Student Emotions

In this section, 18 questions were presented to the students to determine their feelings, emotions, how they perceive themselves, and their levels of happiness and satisfaction with life. In this regard, referring to the Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA, 2022), we see that 75% of Azerbaijani students participating in the survey stated that they easily find friends at school. Similarly, an equal percentage of students feel a sense of belonging to their school. These indicators are at the same level as OECD countries. However, the percentage of Azerbaijani students who feel alone at school is 25%, which is 16% higher than OECD countries. Considering that this survey was conducted only among schools in Baku, it is possible that the results of this survey could be useful for schools in the Agdam region affected by war, in the form of a brochure titled "Experiences Used in Improving the Well-being of Students Affected by War."

Graph 1. Class of the respondents.

Looking at graph 1, we see that 716 of the 782 students of the 9th, 10th and 11th grades of the 10 selected schools participated in the survey. 40% of the students participating in the survey were in the IX class, 30% in the X class, and 30% in the XI class.

Graphic 2. Gender Category .

Looking at Graphic 2, we can observe that among the participants in the survey, 56% were female and 44% were male.

Graph 3. Student emotions.

In graph 3,

42% of the students who answered the first question said that they were not excited, 16% were undecided about answering this question, and 42% said that they felt excited. 39% of the students who answered the second question said they did not feel happy, 16% said they were undecided, and 45% said they felt happy. 38% of the students who answered the third question said that they did not feel pampered and cared for, 17% were undecided in answering this question, and 45% said that they felt pampered and cared for. In the 3th graph, the answers to the questions are reflected as follows. 35% of students who answered the fourth question said they did not feel safe, 15% were undecided, and 50% said they felt safe. 32% of the students who answered the fifth question said that they felt hopeless, 17% said that it was difficult to answer this question, and 51% said that they felt hopeful. 34% of those who answered the sixth question did not feel angry, 14% hesitated to answer this question, and 52% said they felt angry.

Graph 4 Student emotions.

When answering the seventh question in graph 4, 37% of students confirmed that they do not feel alone, 16% were undecided in answering this question, and 47% confirmed that they felt alone. 38% of the students who answered the eighth question said that they did not feel sad, 15% said that they were undecided in answering this question, and 47% said that they felt sad. 34% of those who answered the ninth question did not feel worried, 15% said they had difficulty answering this question, and 51% said they felt worried.

41% of the students who answered the tenth question in the 4th graph said that they did not feel disappointed, 17% said that they hesitated to answer this question, and 42% said that they felt disappointed. 41% of the students who answered the eleventh question said that they were unable to control themselves when an unpleasant incident happened, 15% said that they had difficulty answering this question, and 44% emphasized that they were able to control themselves. 42% of the students who answered the twelfth question stated that they could not calm themselves down when they were afraid, 12% said that they were hesitant to answer this question, and 46% said that they were able to calm themselves down when they were afraid.

Graph 5 Student emotions

48% of the students who answered the thirteenth question from the 5th chart said that they could not control themselves when they were angry, 14% were undecided in answering this question, and 38% said that they were able to calm themselves down when they were angry. 36% of those who answered the fourteenth question stated that they could not control their feelings, 15% said that they had difficulty answering this question, and 49% said that they were able to control their feelings. 41% of the students who answered the fifteenth question said that they could not have a motivational conversation with themselves when they were not feeling well, 13% of the students were undecided about answering this question, and 46% of the students said that they were able to have a motivational conversation with themselves when they were not feeling well.

42% of the students who answered the sixteenth question in chart 8 said that I can't talk to my friend or girlfriend when I don't feel well. 9% of students said that they were undecided in answering this question and 49% of students said that they talk to a friend or girlfriend when they don't feel well. 37% of the respondents who answered the

seventeenth question emphasized that they could not prevent unpleasant thoughts. 19% of students said that they had difficulty answering this question, and 44% said that they were able to avoid it when they had unpleasant thoughts. 39% of those who answered the eighteenth question said that they were unable to cope with their anxiety about the incident, 19% were undecided in answering this question, and 42% stressed that they were able to cope with their anxiety when the incident happened.

2. School environment

Through questions 19-34, students' cooperation with each other, relationships with teachers and other members, whether the school is a loved and safe place for students, in the school and out-of-school environment was possible. Thus, the results of the survey coincide with the results of the International Assessment conducted in Azerbaijan (PISA, 2022). 23% of the Azerbaijani students participating in the PISA survey said that they do not feel safe while going to school and at school. For comparison, let's say that the same indicator for OECD (Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development) countries is only 8%. That is, the indicator recorded in Azerbaijan is almost three times higher than in OECD countries.

One of the notable points about Azerbaijan is the high rate of students not feeling safe even in the classroom. 20% of students from Azerbaijan who participated in the survey said that they do not feel safe in the classrooms. The highest result among the countries participating in the survey on this indicator was recorded in Azerbaijan. The indicator of those who do not feel safe in the classroom is an average of 7% for OECD countries.

Chart 6. School environment.

33% of the students who answered the nineteenth question in graph 6 think that there is no teacher or someone who can help them at school, 9% think that it is difficult to answer this question, and 58% think that there are people who can help them at school. 34% of the students who answered the 20th question said that they don't have a trusted friend at school, 9% found it difficult to answer this question, and 57% said that they have a trusted friend. 35% of the students who answered the twenty-first question think

that there is no one person at school with whom they can feel confident and secure, 13% find it difficult to answer this question, and 52% think that there is a person in school with whom they can feel confident and secure.

31% of the students who answered the twenty-second question in the 6th chart said that they don't have teachers who listen and take them seriously at school, 14% said that it was difficult to answer this question, and 55% said that their teachers listened to them and took them seriously. 30% of the students who answered the twenty-third question said that their teachers did not accept it as it was, 14% said that it was difficult to answer this question, and 56% said that their teachers accepted it as it was. 37% of the students who answered the twenty-fourth question said that they could not trust their teachers, 17% were undecided in answering this question, and 46% said that they trusted their teachers.

Chart 7. School environment

29% of the students who answered the twenty-fifth question in the 7th graph said that their relationship with teachers is not good, 13% hesitated to answer this question, and 58% said that their relationship with teachers is good. 34% of the students who answered the twenty-sixth question said that the teachers did not take care of it, 16% said that it was difficult to answer this question, and 50% said that the teachers took care of it. 37% of the students who answered the twenty-seventh question said that their teachers did not know his strengths, 19% were undecided about answering this question, and 44% said that their teachers knew his strengths.

35% of the students who answered the twenty-eighth question in the 7th graph said that the teachers did not appreciate his abilities, 16% were undecided in answering this question, and 49% said that the teachers appreciated his abilities. 33% of students who answered the twenty-ninth question said that their teachers did not allow them to demonstrate their skills, 16% said that they had difficulty answering this question, and 51% said that their teachers gave them an opportunity to demonstrate their skills. 34% of students who answered the thirtieth question said that they did not feel safe at school, 16% said that they had difficulty finding an answer to this question, and 50% said that they felt safe at school.

Chart 8. School environment

In the 8th graph, 31% of those who answered the thirty-first question said that they did not feel happy at school, 17% were undecided in answering this question, and 52% said that they felt happy at school. 35% of the students who answered the thirty-second question stated that they could not express their thoughts comfortably at school, 15% were undecided about answering this question, and 50% said that they were able to express their thoughts comfortably at school. 30% of the students who answered the thirty-third question said that they do not cooperate with their classmates at school, 16% said that it was difficult to answer this question, and 54% said that they cooperated with their classmates. 41% of the students who answered the thirty-fourth question said that they do not miss school when there is no class, 14% are undecided about answering this question, and 45% said that they miss school when there is no class.

SUGGESTIONS

Planning, preparation, and reconstruction of social life are the future of educational communities (Baran, 2021). Today's school is the society of tomorrow, and today's student is an individual of tomorrow's society. As a social being, individuals have certain responsibilities to themselves and others within the society they live in (Muthanna et al., 2022). Recognizing these responsibilities, along with their innate qualities, and caring for others' well-being, is possible primarily through the upbringing received in the family and later in school, as well as through the relationships experienced (Alemine, 2021). Therefore, it can be said that the family, along with the school, can play the most important role in improving the well-being of students who have suffered from the war (Aydođan & Uygur, 2017). However, the results of the survey show that at least 50% of the students who answered questions related to either "student emotions" or "school environment" are still experiencing the traumas and psychological and emotional problems caused by the war. It is necessary to use the following strategies during the experience and apply innovative methods and approaches in the classroom to create a productive atmosphere (Sezgin & Tinmaz, 2017)."

1. Creating a supportive environment in school: Each student has different strengths, needs, and requirements. Embracing these differences and applying different learning

methods accordingly is essential (Seden et al., 2020). Therefore, school leadership, teachers, class leaders, and psychologists should strive to create a sincere and supportive classroom environment where students feel comfortable and safe. This includes fostering social, emotional, psychological, and academic support, appreciating each student's success, and individualizing approaches (ARTİ, 2021).

2. Involvement of parents in the educational process: The school should work together with the parents of the students to support the students and help them overcome the trauma and psychological stress. For this, the teacher's main activity should include informing parents about their children's needs, wishes, expectations, problems and giving advice on how to help their children (ARTİ, 2021).

3. Physical and emotional activity at school: Physical and emotional activities at school play an important role in promoting student well-being (Liu et al., 2016). Students who engage in regular physical activity are usually better able to cope with stress. Teachers can involve students in intra-school, district and regional sports competitions, intellectual and social competitions, debates or other physical activities during school hours or after school.

4. School is a place for students to have fun and socialize: It is known that in the villages of Agdam region, where students suffering from the war live, there is no place for students to communicate with each other, an entertainment center, a playground, a recreation park and other social infrastructures. The school organizes theater, concerts, exhibitions, etc. cultural and social events such as.

5. Teaching students stress management skills: Teaching students stress management skills is an important step in developing their well-being and learning habits (Sezgin and Tinmaz, 2017). Natural disasters, pandemics, and wars occurring in the world cause psychological tension among people. This tension leads to disruption of interpersonal relations, increase of intra-family conflicts, deepening of stress and fear in children and adolescents. Providing psycho-social support according to the need to overcome the listed problems is a successful way out according to research. Schools and teachers have an indispensable role in relieving stress and tension of students affected by the conflict (Sezgin and Tinmaz, 2017).

6. School is the basis of cooperation: School cooperation is based on partnership, good understanding and ability to work together among management, teachers and students. For this, teachers can organize group discussions for students to share their experiences, problems and stresses (Liu et al., 2016). It helps students to realize that they are not alone in their problems, to share their feelings with each other, and to give and receive support and advice from their peers.

7. Student participation in decision-making: Teachers can involve students in decision-making, such as the method and method of organizing the lesson, choosing projects, identifying research topics, or choosing assessment methods, and invite students to vote

on the topic of an upcoming project or a final paper for presentation. how many formats they can offer (Liu et al., 2016). Students' participation in decision-making positively affects their learning processes and helps them take responsibility.

8. Understanding students' self-confidence and strengths: Teachers must use a variety of tools to help students discover their strengths. Self-confidence means realizing your own worth and potential. It helps students to increase their awareness of their abilities, interests and goals. At this time, it becomes easier to achieve success and achieve goals (Vranda, 2015). Understanding their strengths helps students understand and develop their potential.

9. Conducting seminars and master-classes at school: School leaders can invite successful role models and experts in the field of well-being to conduct seminars and master-classes (Babayeva and Omarova, 2021). Workshops and masterclasses are an effective way for teachers to support students' psychological health, increase academic achievement, connect with successful role models, and learn from well-being experts.

10. Strategies for coping with exam stress: Positive thoughts and words of encouragement, support from family members and teachers play an important role in coping with exam stress (Kinley et al., 2020). Teachers and parents are well aware that students living in the region have serious war-related traumas. On top of that, it is not so difficult to imagine the situation of those students when it comes to the stress of university preparation, graduation and entrance exams. Each teacher can help students develop strategies for coping with exam stress, including preparation, time management, relaxation, and peer support.

11. Training school administrators and teachers: School administrators and teachers should be trained to deal with war trauma, stress, and attention problems in students. These exercises will provide individual and collective experiences on how to help school management and teachers to support students, provide moral and psychological help. This is an important step for students to get a good education and be psychologically healthy, to feel in a safe environment at school and to build confidence (Maya Vafki, 2019).

Result: This article investigates the significant role of schools in enhancing the well-being of students affected by war. Students experiencing the negative impacts of war face emotional, psychological, and academic difficulties. The support provided by schools to these students plays a crucial role in improving their quality of life.

The article emphasizes that schools can apply various methods and strategies to understand the needs and improve the well-being of students affected by war. Psychological support programs, individualized education plans, and community support are essential to ensure the academic and emotional development of these students. Additionally, it is important to provide teachers and school staff with the necessary training and resources to work with these students.

In conclusion, we can state that schools can serve as a powerful tool for the reintegration of war-affected students into society and for enhancing their well-being. The support from schools helps these students become healthier and more productive individuals in the future. More research and implementation projects are needed in this area to continuously improve the well-being of students affected by war.

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